

ESCALATOR PROGRESS REPORT

2020 – 2024

science & innovation

Department:
Science and Technology
REPUBLIC OF SOUTH AFRICA

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INTRODUCTION

Scholarly work across the humanities, as in all academic fields, is increasingly being done digitally. The particular contribution of the digital humanities, however, lies in its exploration of the difference that the digital can make to the kinds of work that we do, as well as to the ways that we communicate with one another.

Kathleen Fitzpatrick, 2011

The South African Centre for Digital Language Resources (SADiLaR) is a national research infrastructure that is part of the South African Research Infrastructure Roadmap. Its strategic function is to create, manage, and distribute digital language resources and applicable software for all official languages in South Africa through its digitisation programme, while through its digital humanities (DH) programme, SADiLaR stimulates and supports computational research and development in the humanities and social sciences (HSS).

SADiLaR created the ESCALATOR programme to address the critical need for human capacity development in the field of digital humanities. ESCALATOR is unique in the sense that it offers a range of entry points and aims to meet participants where they are at, regardless of their skill level. The programme includes introductory sessions, awareness creation opportunities, networking platforms, as well as spaces where more advanced learning can take place.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

ESCALATOR is a capacity and community development programme which formally commenced on 1 December 2020. It aims to support the development of an active and inclusive community of practice in digital humanities (DH) and computational social science (CSS) in South Africa. The programme was developed through a collaboration between the South African Centre for Digital Language Resources (SADiLaR) and Talarify. As of May 2024, it is undergoing a critical review and strategic re-alignment.

The first draft of the programme was developed pre-COVID-19. The programme would facilitate awareness creation and skills development through in-person and virtual nationwide events. Throughout, individuals would be identified to act as champions in their institutions.

Despite 45% of the programme duration overlapping COVID-19 restrictions, ESCALATOR reached 25 of the 26 Universities South Africa (USAf) members over the past three and a half years. Participants in the programme also represented research councils such as the Human Research Council (HSRC), Agricultural Research Council (ARC), Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), and numerous other organisations.

In 2021, the DHCSSza Slack channel was created to provide a platform for networking, information sharing, and online learning. To date, 393 members have joined the space where hundreds of opportunities for education, networking, funding, and more have been shared.

As part of the ESCALATOR programme, regional DH-IGNITE events were implemented to compensate for lost time and reach community members in person. Five events occurred between October 2022 and April 2024, reaching 397 participants, presenters, and exhibitors from 46 organisations.

More than 350 responses to the question “What are your biggest challenges in adopting digital/computational practices in your research?” were collected via the DH-IGNITE registration form. The data represent the views of staff and students at various career stages in multiple areas of humanities and social sciences research at almost all public universities. A preliminary analysis shows that the most significant challenges relate to a lack of knowledge and skills and access to financial resources, data in digital formats, and training.

This finding aligns well with observations from interactions with the community through various ESCALATOR activities. Many Humanities and Social Sciences (HSS) scholars are still inept at using and, in many cases, utterly unaware of digital resources, technologies and methodologies across the breadth of the research lifecycle (not only when it comes to data analysis).

We will only have a thriving digital humanities and computational social science research community if our HSS scholars are better equipped to engage with digital technologies across the research life cycle to enhance their research. Once scholars are adept at employing digital technologies across the research lifecycle, they can more efficiently progress to critically and productively engage with profound questions around the impact of digital artefacts that touch our lives and shape our societies. This kind of research relies heavily on interdisciplinary, inter-institutional collaborations enabled through participation in communities of practice and the use of various digital platforms. On the positive side, there are pockets of excellence in select research groupings where digital and computational methodologies are embedded in research design and implementation.

PROGRAMME REACH

 University of Port Hare <i>Together in Excellence</i>	✓		
 UNIVERSITY OF JOHANNESBURG	✓		
 UNIVERSITY OF KWAZULU-NATAL INYUVESI YAKWAZULU-NATALI	✓		
 UNIVERSITY OF LIMPOPO	✓		
 UNIVERSITY OF MPUMALANGA <i>Creating Opportunities</i>	✓		
 UNIVERSITEIT VAN PRETORIA UNIVERSITY OF PRETORIA YUNIBESITHI YA PRETORIA	✓		
 UNIVERSITY OF THE FREE STATE UNIVERSITEIT VAN DIE VRYSTAAT YUNIBESITHI YA FREESTATA	✓		
 UNIVERSITY OF THE WITWATERSRAND JOHANNESBURG	✓		
 University of Venda	✓		
 UNIVERSITY of the WESTERN CAPE	✓		
 UNIVERSITY OF ZULULAND	✓		
 WSU Walter Sisulu University	✓		
 VAAL UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY <i>Inspiring thought. Shaping talent.</i>	✓		

ESCALATOR TIMELINE

December 2020 - May 2024

PROGRAMME DESIGN

PROGRAMME DESIGN

ESCALATOR was developed with the following audiences in mind:

- Primary:
 - HSS researchers at all career stages
 - HSS research management (e.g. deans, school directors, etc.)
 - HSS postgraduate students
- Secondary:
 - Academic librarians working in areas of HSS support or research
 - Academic library management
- Additionally:
 - Research infrastructure providers (to ensure their infrastructure addresses the needs of HSS research)
 - Researchers and postgraduate students in traditionally more computational research fields

COMMUNITY NEEDS AND EXPECTATIONS

The community needs analysis is critical to ESCALATOR's success. The primary target audience represents a wide range of sub-disciplines within HSS, career stages, research interests, digital skill levels, experience with interdisciplinary research, and embeddedness within professional networks. This tremendous diversity impacts the ability of ESCALATOR to be perceived as successful by individuals participating in the programme.

An initial informal needs analysis was compiled from responses received through the "Needs Assessment" form and conversations with various stakeholders.

The primary needs identified included:

- Limited visibility and findability of training opportunities
- Lack of entry-level training resources and opportunities
- Lack of training opportunities in more advanced DH/CSS topics
- Lack of contextualised training resources
- Difficulty to find South African research groups, projects, and publications within DH and CSS
- Limited opportunities to become involved in the local DH/CSS community

Based on prior experience in needs assessments related to topics perceived to be relatively novel (e.g. open science, research data management, etc.), we know that it is difficult for participants to define challenges and needs clearly (they don't know what they don't know). Instead of launching a multi-question survey to explore this topic within our primary target audience, we included two questions in the DH-IGNITE registration forms:

- *What are your biggest challenges in adopting digital/computational practices in your research?*
- *What do you hope to get out of attending the event?*

More than 350 responses were received from 25 out of 26 public universities, the HSRC, CSIR, and other relevant institutions.

The following themes were amongst the top 20 significant challenges identified in a preliminary analysis:

Theme	Number of responses
knowledge gap	72
skills gap	65
access to data	37
financial challenges	34
access to training	33
access to infrastructure	24
data analysis skills	24
digital scholarship	22
limited resources	21
time constraints	19

Theme	Number of responses
lack of contextual examples	18
access to information	17
difficult software /complex workflows	16
access to software	15
adapting to new methods	12
buy-in	7
experienced collaborators	7
internet access	7
lack of role models	7
fit-for-purpose software	6

The main themes identified through the preliminary analysis of the responses to the question about participants' expectations for DH-IGNITE are shown below:

Theme	Number of responses
learn	611
engage with peers	101
advice on own research	18
access	6
share information about existing resources	6
assess status of DH in SA	4
gain confidence	4
collaboration with SADiLaR	3
inspiration	3
ethics	2
help build regional community	2
publishing manuscripts/blogs/other	2
build profile	1
financial assistance	1
increase accessibility for colleagues with disabilities	1
mentorship	1

IMPLEMENTATION

The ESCALATOR programme was designed with the help of a Theory of Change to ensure activities and outputs can lead to the envisioned impact.

The programme is built on three pillars, each contributing to the overarching goals of skill development, community building, resource sharing, driving innovation, and increasing the visibility of South African DH research on the global stage

DH-IGNITE events

A series of events designed to introduce newcomers to the field of Digital Humanities and build a vibrant community of practitioners.

Training & Champions Initiative

A multi-track system offering tailored learning pathways for individuals at various stages of their DH journey, from curious beginners to seasoned experts.

Stakeholder map

An interactive platform aimed at connecting researchers, students, industry professionals, and academic institutions to facilitate collaboration and resource sharing within the DH community.

DH-IGNITE

Igniting a spark

WHAT IS IT?

DH-IGNITE events are interdisciplinary, intergenerational gatherings bringing together researchers, students, research management, librarians, language practitioners and more. During these events, participants are introduced to the ESCALATOR programme and various concepts related to Digital Humanities at the hand of real-world projects.

WHERE DO I FIND IT?

Between 2022 and 2024, DH-IGNITEs were run in five regions, bringing together participants from 25 public universities and three research councils. More than 350 participants were reached.

Recently DH-IGNITE MINIs were launched. These events are associated with conferences and are typically shorter.

WHERE CAN I LEARN MORE?

All resources created during the events are available on the ESCALATOR website.

LEARN MORE

DIGITAL TRAINING AND CHAMPIONS INITIATIVE

Growing together

The ESCALATOR Training and Champions Initiative is a multi-track awareness creation and capacity development programme. Each track offers a variety of activities either in person or online. Information about the tracks and corresponding activities are available on the ESCALATOR website.

[LEARN MORE](#) >>

EXPLORER

Your gateway to DH

The Explorer Track offers a starting point for newcomers to ESCALATOR programme and DH in general. The track offers a variety of low commitment engagements for community members from diverse backgrounds.

Purpose	Activities	Target audience
Familiarise community members with ESCALATOR	Onboarding activities	Anyone interested in learning more about ESCALATOR and how to get involved.
Showcase what is happening in the DH community	DH Colloquia series organised by SADIaR	Researchers, students, professional academic staff.
Provide an entry point for scholars who are new to DH	YouTube Channel with variety of playlists	Anyone interested in learning foundational DH concepts or wanting to access event recordings.

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EMBARKER

Where your DH adventure begins

The Embarker Track offers a range of foundational training opportunities under the “First Steps” series. To date, courses have focused on an introduction to programming in Python and R. New opportunities are forthcoming.

First Steps courses are offered in small groups to ensure instructors can provide individual guidance to participants.

Purpose	Activities	Target audience
Provide foundational skills in programming in Python	First Steps to Python for Humanities and Social Sciences	HSS researchers and students with no prior experience with programming.
Provide foundational skills in programming in R	First Steps to R for Humanities and Social Sciences	HSS researchers and students with no prior experience with programming.

[LEARN MORE](#)

ENHANCER

Taking Your DH Expertise to the Next Level

The Enhancer Track provide opportunities to develop advance skills for those already competent in digital research. This track is geared towards growing leaders in Digital Humanities research who can also train the next generation of DH researchers. Typically participants in this track are already embedded in DH research where they can directly apply and practice the newly acquired skills.

Purpose	Activities	Target audience
Learn advanced skills in open science and interdisciplinary collaboration	Open Seeds Mentoring and Training Programme	HSS researchers with project ideas that requires learning new skills and growing their networks.
Regular dedicated opportunities to practice programming with peers in a supportive environment	R & Python virtual study groups	HSS researchers and students already working on DH programming projects

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ENABLER

*Helping others to develop
DH capabilities*

The Enabler track is focused on the needs of people working in support roles, for example within faculties, the library, eResearch offices, or research support offices. The main aim is to provide participants with useful guides and resources to help them grow the local community in digital humanities and computational social science at their institution.

EDUCATOR

*Shaping Open Knowledge
for DH*

The aim of the Educator track is to provide support for the development of contextualised open educational resources (OER) to enable digital research skills development and DH research in South Africa.

ESCALATOR partnered with the NWU UNESCO Chair in Multimodal Learning and OERs to deliver a short course on OER development and seed funding. 25 projects were spearheaded by project teams from 14 public universities in South Africa.

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EMPOWER

*Amplifying Women's Voices
in DH*

The Empower track builds on the knowledge that women are still underrepresented in tech communities. Activities under this track aim to ensure women are central to digital transformation in HSS research and provide opportunities for women in HSS research to connect with existing and emerging tech communities.

Events are aligned with local and international calendars to coincide with International Women's Day and South Africa Women's Month.

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EXECUTIVE

*Bridging Vision and Action
in DH*

The Executive track aims to facilitate discussions on updating curricula to include digital and computational learning and practices in HSS. It provides forums for sharing progress, challenges, and opportunities in curriculum development, funding and digital innovation.

LEARN MORE

ENGAGER

Making DH accessible to all

The Engager track aims to share the benefits and awareness of DH with the broader public through workshops and public engagement events. By enhancing public awareness of digital and computational opportunities in HSS, this track provides opportunities to attract more interest from potential students to join the growing field of DH in South Africa.

To date, the main activity under this track has been the SWiP project, a collaboration between SADiLaR, Wikipedia, and the Pan South African Language Board (PanSALB).

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EXCHANGER

Interdisciplinarity - the key to DH success

The Exchanger track provides dedicated opportunities for interdisciplinary conversation and collaboration. This track ensures that HSS researchers and those from traditionally more computational backgrounds engage to share skills and expertise to enhance the impact in both disciplines.

STAKEHOLDER MAP

Connecting the dots

WHAT IS IT?

The DHCSSza Stakeholder Map directly addresses one of the core needs identified: enhancing the visibility of individuals, research groups, projects, and other resources related to DH in South Africa. The map name is an acronym for Digital Humanities (DH) and Computational Social Sciences (CSS) in South Africa (za).

The DHCSSza map was developed using open-source technologies, transferable tools, and workflows following the open science principles upon which ESCALATOR is built. All scripts and design decisions were described in a four-part blog series published on the ESCALATOR website. The scripts are available under open licenses on the DHCSSza Github repository.

WHERE DO I FIND IT?

Community members can add their or others' information via a Google Form. The form submission is captured in a Google Sheet, which is manipulated via various R scripts to create a tabular data set that can be accessed and visualised on a map via an interactive Shiny application online. The Shiny app is embedded in the ESCALATOR website to ensure community members can find the stakeholder map easily. An interactive network analysis is shown via Kumu.io, which is also embedded in the website.

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NEXT STEPS

ESCALATOR is currently undergoing a critical review and strategic re-alignment to ensure the relevance and sustainability of its activities. The main aim of this phase is to engage more active community members and create opportunities for leadership development. Furthermore the programme team are exploring ways to make the programme more accessible to all.

1

Strategic re-alignment

SADiLaR team members are actively taking on lead roles to continue driving ESCALATOR activities

2

Engaging the community

To grow ESCALATOR's reach and impact, members of the community will be invited to contribute leadership and collaborate

3

Streamlining participant experience

The project will ensure that participants can find relevant information in a timely fashion and easily engage with the community

CONCLUSION

The ESCALATOR programme is aligned with the long-term outcomes of the Department of Science and Innovation's 2022 - 2032 Science, Technology and Innovation Decadal Plan:

“

a productive NSI contributing to the following: (a) economic growth and inclusivity; (b) social development; (c) environmental sustainability; (d) strong institutions, and (e) a capable state.

”

Through the digital transformation of HSS research and education, graduates will be better equipped for impact in the various areas served by humanities and social sciences, including education, government, mental health, economic development, social development, people and culture, language, and more. HSS researchers will be empowered to grapple with the impact of the digitalisation of society and contribute to knowledge that will aid in creating more just, equitable and healthy societies for the generations to come.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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COVER IMAGE

Generated by DALL-E 3 with the following *prompt*:

An illustration for a report cover. At the bottom, there are various computers, code snippets, and digital symbols like binary code, circuit boards, and data streams, representing computational references. As the image flows upwards, these elements gradually transform into diverse people of different ethnicities and genders, symbolizing a blend of technology and humanity. The transition is seamless, showing a blend from a digital to a human form. The background is a gradient, transitioning from a cool blue at the bottom to a warm, inviting color at the top.

Contact

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